

Contextual Determinants in the Performance of Sports Coaches in Sultan Kudarat

Alvin E. Magbanua, EdD ¹
1 – Sultan Kudarat State University

Publication Date: May 23, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15501691

Abstract

Sports coaching plays a crucial role in athlete development, yet it remains an underexplored area and is often perceived as non-problematic. The effectiveness of coaching programs depends significantly on the dedication, expertise, and motivation of coaches. This study aimed to assess the performance of sports coaches in Sultan Kudarat by examining the influence of their personal characteristics, professional quality, and motivational factors. Using a quantitative, descriptive-correlational design, the research involved survey data from 40 sports coaches and 40 athletes.

The results showed that 30% of coaches were aged 39–45, 72% were male, and 75% were married. A majority (65%) held a master's degree, while 55% had 10–14 years of coaching experience. About 60% of the coaches were classified as having intermediate competency, and 57.5% used sports facilities three times per week. High satisfaction levels were reported

regarding administrative and human resource support in state colleges and universities. Most coaches had a personal interest in coaching and were former athletes. However, their participation in international competitions was limited, with most having competed only 3–4 times in local or regional events over the past five years.

Significant correlations were found between coaching performance and the coaches' characteristics, quality, and motivation. Educational attainment and coaching experience emerged as key determinants of performance. The study concluded that a coach's performance is strongly influenced by their educational background, years of experience, and motivational factors. These findings emphasize the importance of continuous professional development to enhance the effectiveness of sports coaching.

Keywords: Sports Coaches, Sports Development, Motivation of Sports Coaches, Performance of Sports Coaches, Contextual Determinants of Sports Coaches

Introduction

There is little doubt that sports coaching has gained increasing significance in recent years. The publication of *Coaching Matters* (Coaching Review Panel, 1991) both highlighted and consolidated this

growing attention, serving as a pivotal reference for ongoing research and development in the field. The contribution of coaches to enhancing sports participation has been recognized (National Coaching Foundation, 1993), and their vital role in fostering excellence in sport is widely acknowledged (Department of National Heritage, 1995; Scottish Sports Council, 1994).

As such, a major concern for policymakers is ensuring an adequate supply of qualified coaches who can help boost participation and raise performance standards. In this context, examining recruitment practices and understanding the motivations behind individuals becoming coaches is a legitimate and timely concern. Despite this increased prominence, coaching and coaches have often been treated as non-problematic topics, receiving limited attention in academic research (Lyle, 1996). There remains a lack of high-quality empirical studies on coaching practice, posing a risk that policy decisions may be made without a solid evidence base.

It is also worth noting that much of the extensive North American literature on coaching focuses on coaches within formal institutional settings—such as high schools, colleges, and universities—where coaching is often part of a structured career path. In contrast, over 100,000 coaches in the UK, as estimated by the Coaching Review Panel (1991), operate primarily as volunteer club coaches. The Scottish Sports Council (1995) has emphasized the critical role these volunteers play:

"The provision of coaching relies substantially on the goodwill, dedication, and expertise of a voluntary workforce."

Their time, effort, and high standards are essential to the development of sport in Scotland. To sustain and enhance this vital contribution, it is crucial to gain a deeper understanding of the factors that motivate coaches to engage in their work.

Mentors and coaches exert a significant influence over athletes, particularly in identifying and nurturing talent. A coach's characteristics, quality, and motivational orientation can greatly affect athlete performance and long-term participation in sports.

While several studies have examined coaching behavior in various universities and colleges, there is a notable gap in the literature when it comes to evaluating coaching performance based on characteristics, quality, and motivation, especially in the local context. Therefore, an empirical investigation is necessary to examine the contextual determinants affecting the performance of sports coaches in Sultan Kudarat.

The main purpose of this study is to determine the contextual determinants of the performance of coaches in Higher Education Institutions in Sultan Kudarat over the past five years (2014–2019). Findings from this study will serve as the basis for proposing a contextualized coaching performance model.

Method

Design, Selection, Study Site, and Instrumentation

This research methodology covers the research design that explains the survey method of the study on how the data will be gathered. It additionally portrays the research environment that depicts the climate of where the investigation is to be conducted. It explains and describes the respondents of the study. The instruments also are analyzed which are to be used in conducting the survey. It gives the thought on how the data will be gathered, treated, analyzed, and interpreted. There will be no follow-up interview to be given to the respondents; they will just answer the standardized tests given. This gives an overview of how the research methodology will be done.

The study used the quantitative design that involves collecting, analyzing, and integrating quantitative research. Descriptive Correlational Research Design was used for the quantitative method. This is a non-experimental research method that would measure the two (2) variables, understand and assess their statistical relationship.

The survey method through a questionnaire would be adopted by the researcher in gathering the data to determine the contextual determinants in the performances of sports coaches in Sultan Kudarat.

Choosing the participants of the study with appropriate and various experiences increases the possibility of shedding light on the research problem (Granheim & Lundman, 2004).

The participants of the study are the coaches of Higher Education Institutions in Sultan Kudarat. Their age bracket is 20–60. They are all professional coaches and athletes; in fact, they start to assume the responsibility of being dynamic and enthusiastic coaching instructors and athletes in HEI's.

In the quantitative method, there is no sampling technique to be used in the study since complete enumeration is being used in this study. To identify the participants of the study, the researcher set the following criteria:

For the sports coaches:

- (a) He/she is of legal age;
- (b) He/she must be a government or private employee, either permanent or contract of service of HEI's in Sultan Kudarat;
- (c) He/she must be a champion coach; and,
- (d) He/she is willing to be interviewed and participate in the survey.

For the student-athletes:

- (a) He/she must belong to team sports;
- (b) He/she is a performing athlete at the local/regional or national level;
- (c) He/she is willing to be interviewed and participate in the survey.

These participants are capable and able to answer the questionnaires since they can easily relate the content of the study, for it speaks about their sports. The researcher believes that the study suits their level of interest and ability that would not cause any harm to them but an inspiration to strive for success and excellence.

The instruments are very important in a study in order to gather data. Likewise, it provides the data to have a statistical presentation that supports the study to come up with a positive result. The researcher utilized modified instruments and interview schedules. The modified instrument contains six (6) parts. The following are the instruments which the study needs to have:

The tool that determined the general information of participants in terms of personal information, educational attainment, sports experience, and coaching certification/license.

Data Collection and Ethical Consideration

For the data analysis, after collecting the data—which are the distributed questionnaires and quotient of coaches' performance—these were processed, presented, analyzed, and interpreted parallel to the problem.

The data was collected using survey questionnaires. Descriptive analysis (Mann, 1995) was utilized using the frequency response distribution, which included the computation of the mean. Descriptive Correlation Design (Stangor, 2011) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Sedgwick, 2012) were utilized to explain the significant relationship between the performance and characteristics, quality, and motivation. Also, Adversity Quotient is used in determining the extent of motivation of sports coaches in terms of continued involvement in coaching. This is based on the characteristics, quality, and motivation to describe its Score Range and Equivalents.

Research needs principled deliberations to make it morally sound and strengthen the validity and reliability for its quality standards. This has been designed for the protection of the participants and to avoid risk during the conduct of the study. Thus, the researcher considers the privacy and confidentiality of the participants for its integrity. If they felt uncomfortable in answering the given questionnaire, they would not be forced to give their answer, and they could proceed to the next question. Whatever answers and information gathered would be kept with confidentiality. The researcher valued the readiness of the participants to answer; if they would feel that they were not yet ready to answer, then the researcher would understand and respect their decision. There would be another schedule to be set for the convenience of the participants.

The researcher would explain to the participants about the purpose of the study and would inform them that their honest answers could help the success of the study. Moreover, they deserved to be protected from any risk and emotional harm that the study may cause. The participants would be informed ahead of time so that they would be ready in answering the questionnaire. There would be no monetary involvement, such as for transportation of the students, since the study was conducted during school days and other related activities that involve money. Thus, the participants would be informed that this is voluntary, and they would not be paid for their participation, but they were highly appreciated for cooperating in the success of the study. They would be oriented about the importance of the study and the value of their answers, and it must be kept confidentially for their safety.

Furthermore, the researcher, by virtue of the guidelines prescribed by the university, should fully comply with all requirements in the conduct of the study. Before the study will be carried out, the project would undergo ethical review and approval by the Institutional Review Board (IRB), which is the ethics committee in the university. Thus, it adheres to the principles of the Belmont Report on standards of ethical conduct in research.

Results and Discussions

This study is geared towards the determinants of coaches in Sultan Kudarat. This study aimed to provide an interpretation of the quality of coaches in Sultan Kudarat. The study used a Quasi-experimental design wherein the survey takes place for four (4) months.

The forty (40) coaches and forty (40) athletes of state colleges and universities in Sultan Kudarat are the subjects of this study. Their contextual determinants were documented through the questionnaire. The research evaluated the characteristic, quality, and motivation of coaches from state and university in Sultan Kudarat.

The following are the findings of the study:

1. **Characteristics of Sports Coaches in terms of age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, sports experience, and coaching certification/license.**
Coaching is for everybody or individuals who are involved in different sports, but more of our sports coaches in Sultan Kudarat are male.
This is similar to the statement of Eagly and Karaw (2000), who have demonstrated that women in leadership positions, such as sports coaching, tend to be rated as less effective in comparison to men in the same position.
Characteristics in terms of age are from twenty-five (25) years old to fifty-nine (59) years old.
Further, it shows that the coaches aged twenty-five (25) to thirty-one (31) years old have a frequency of eleven (11); thirty-two (32) to thirty-eight (38) years old have a frequency of five (5); thirty-nine (39) to forty-five (45) years old have a frequency of twelve (12); forty-six (46) to fifty-two (52) years old have a frequency of six (6); and fifty-three (53) to fifty-nine (59) years old have a frequency of six (6).
The age of coaches most responsive in terms of coaching are between thirty-nine (39) to forty-five (45) years old, followed by twenty-five (25) to thirty-one (31) years old.
Also, married coaches have a frequency of thirty (30), and single coaches have a frequency of ten (10). Most coaches engaging in the coaching profession are married in terms of civil status.
Furthermore, coaches who are master's degree holders in terms of educational attainment have a frequency of twenty-six (26), followed by doctorate degree holders with a frequency of fourteen (14). Most coaches involved in coaching are master's degree holders, more experienced, and knowledgeable in coaching.
It is similar to the statement that coaches who understand different learning styles and preferences tend to be more effective, which has implications for coach education content and presenter (Cassidy, Potrac, & McKenzie, 2006).
2. **Quality of Facilities and Equipment, Administrative Support, and Human Resources**
The mean of the quality of facility and equipment for sports coaches and athletes is 3.7, described as "very satisfied," and the mean of using facility and equipment is 3.52, described as "very satisfied." This means that most coaches use facilities and equipment during players' or athletes' training.
According to EKPC (2001), the success of any sports program depends largely on the quality and quantity of available facilities and equipment.
Human resources-related issues and Administrative Support among the faculty, staff, and administrators in different state colleges and universities in Region 12 are rated "highly satisfied."
3. **Extent of Motivation of Sports Coaches**
The extent of motivation to the selection of quality coaches. It is noted that personal interest has a frequency of thirty-seven (37), rated rank number one (1). Former athletes are a motivation for being a quality and good coach, rated rank number two (2). Academic background has a frequency of ten (10), rated rank three (3), and is also considered a factor that can be attributed to the selection of quality coaches.
The coaches engaged in sports coaching by their passion, like individual interest, previous athlete or player, and he or she graduated in physical education.
4. **Performance of Coaches in terms of Accomplishment in the Last 5 Years**

Sports coaches have a very poor performance at the international level of competition, and most of the coaches participated only 3–4 times at the local/regional level in the last five years.

This revealed that seventy (70) percent of the coaches have poor performance because local/regional-level sports competitions happen only once every year.

5. Highest Awards and Recognition During Sports Competition

The frequency of awards and recognition of coaches gathered zero awards in international competition. But three (3) gold, thirty-two (32) silver, sixteen (16) bronze, and four (4) top finalists for the national level for the past five (5) years.

At this level, coaches' awards and recognition show that they are leading in silver rather than gold.

6. Contextual Determinants of Sports Coaches

The ratio of academic background, employment opportunity, and former is 0.43, and the P-value is 0.006 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. To claim that the background of being a coach is a leading factor in the performance of a coach.

7. Degree of Relationship Between Performance and Characteristic, Quality, and Motivation

An inspection of the table connecting the performance and characteristic is $r = 0.78$ and a probability of 0.006, and the performance and quality is $r = 0.36$ and a probability of 0.023, while performance and motivation have $r = 0.78$ and a probability of 0.006 at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance.

This proves that the performance of coaches differs as influenced by characteristics, quality, and motivations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Coaching background, coaching experiences, and coaching supports serve to determine coaches from Sultan Kudarat. This study concludes that educational attainment, being former athletes, licensed coaches, training experience, coaching achievements, administrative experience, motivation in coaching, having initiative supports, and quality training supports significantly affect their quality as coaches as a whole.

Recommendations:

- There must be proper application determination about selecting qualified sports coaches.
- The developed model may be implemented in all State and Universities as one of the bases for selecting qualified sports coaches.
- Future researchers are encouraged to develop their model to improve this study.

References

- Acosta, R.V. & Carpenter, L.J. (1985). Women in sport. In Donald Chu, Jeffrey O. Segrave & Beverly J. Becker (Eds.), *Sport and Higher Education* (pp.313-325). Champaign, IL. Human Kinetics
- Bielous, G. A. (1994). Effective coaching: Improving marginal performers. *Supervision*, 55(7), 35
- Bierema, L. (1996). Development of the individual leads to more productive workplaces. In R. W. Boles, J.K. (1989). A policy of our own: Local feminist networks and social services for women and children. *Policy Studies Review*, 8(3), 638-647.
- Burdett, J. O. (1998). Forty things every manager should know about coaching. *Journal of Management Development*, 17(2), 142-152.
- Carpenter, L.J. & Acosta, R.V. (2005). *Title IX*. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
- Carpenter, L.J. (1993). *Letters home: My life with Title IX*. In G.L. Cohen (Ed). *Women in Sport: Issues and Controversies*. (pp 133-155), Newberry Park, CA.: Sage Publishing.
- Chafe, W.H. (1972). *The American woman: Her changing social, economic and political roles, 1920-1970*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Clarke, E. H. (1874). *Sex in education; or, a fair chance for girls*. Boston: James R. Osgood and Company.
- Ellinger, A. D., & Bostrom, R. P. (1999). Managerial coaching behaviors in learning organizations. *Journal of Management Development*, 18(9), 752-771.
- Ellinger, A. M. (1997). *Managers as facilitators of learning in learning organizations*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Georgia.